

COMMUNICATIVE STRATEGIES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS TOWARDS WORKSHOP MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary globalized world, the English language plays a pivotal role in international communication and education, transcending linguistic boundaries to connect people and open doors to diverse opportunities. The importance of English in education cannot be overstated, as it enhances students' communication abilities, impacting academic success and professional development. Effective communication is fundamental to human society, and teachers are crucial in nurturing students' communicative competence. However, challenges persist in effectively implementing communicative strategies in the classroom. This study aims to assess English language teachers' proficiency in teaching sociolinguistic competence, examine students' communication strategies, and propose a Workshop Matrix to enhance the use of communicative strategies, benefiting students in their English language learning journey. The study's findings reveal that teachers employ various communicative strategies, positively influencing students' intrapersonal and interpersonal skills. Recommendations include teacher training, student development, continued research, curriculum enhancement, and collaboration to create a more effective and engaging learning environment for English language learners.

Keywords: workshop matrix, communicative strategies, intrapersonal and interpersonal skills

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, the English language stands as a cornerstone of international communication, playing a pivotal role in numerous industries, including medicine, engineering, and education. English is not merely a language; it is a bridge connecting people worldwide and opening doors to diverse opportunities. Its significance in the field of education cannot be overstated, as it permeates subjects and boosts students' confidence and competitiveness on a global scale. Language is not merely a subject; it is a life skill that enhances educational attainment through improved communication abilities, impacting academic success and

professional development. It also serves as a powerful emblem of social behavior, conveying essential social signals about individuals' backgrounds, affiliations, and intentions.

Effective communication is a fundamental aspect of human society, facilitating interaction and growth. Individuals are natural communicators, engaged in various forms of communication daily. Teachers play a crucial role in nurturing their students' communicative competence, enhancing their knowledge, skills, and attitudes for effective communication with individuals from diverse backgrounds. It is crucial for teachers to apply communicative strategies effectively, fostering a diverse and immersive learning environment that encourages students to communicate confidently in the target language.

However, despite the importance of communicative strategies in language teaching, challenges persist in their effective application in the classroom. Many teachers may struggle to understand how to implement these strategies appropriately, which can impact students' language development. This study aims to address these challenges and enhance communicative strategies among teachers, ultimately benefiting students in their English language learning journey. The results will serve as a strong foundation for the development of workshops aimed at improving the use of communicative strategies in teaching English, fostering a more effective and engaging learning environment for students, and enhancing their proficiency and confidence in the English language.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the communicative strategies of English Language Teachers in Division of Batangas Province.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of utilization of the following communicative strategies:

- 1.1 Nomination;
- 1.2 Restriction and Turn Taking;
- 1.3 Topic Control and Shifting;
- 1.4 Repair; and
- 1.5 Termination?

2. How do students' communication strategies assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal and interpersonal?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of utilization of comm strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal and interpersonal?

4. Based on the findings, what Workshop Matrix may be proposed for the enhancement of the use of communicative strategies in teaching English?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive in its attempt to describe the communicative strategies of English Language Teachers. This design was deemed to be the most appropriate to analyze and interpret the data to be collected during the research period. The process of descriptive research goes beyond the mere collection and tabulation of information and data. It involves the interpretation of the meaning of what is described. As Baraceros (2016) stated, descriptive research describes and interprets what is. It is concerned with conditions of relationships that

exist, practices that prevail; beliefs, processes that are going on; effects that are being felt, or trends that are developing. Its importance is based on the premise of problem solving and enhancing practices through observation, analysis and description. Moreover, the study used the questionnaire as primary tool for data gathering, which was complemented by the conduct of interviews to the English Language teachers in the province of Batangas.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the extent of utilization of various communicative strategies and relationship between the extent of utilization of comm strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal and interpersonal?

Table 1
English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Nomination

	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. state the objectives clearly at the start of the class.	3.73	0.45	GE
2. say what is relevant to the topic.	3.75	0.45	GE
3. give a question about the topic.	3.70	0.52	GE
4. get the students' attention.	3.72	0.46	GE
5. present the lesson with empathy.	3.70	0.46	GE
6. give clues about the topic.	3.67	0.51	GE
7. check the students' background knowledge.	3.65	0.51	GE
8. establish the topic clearly.	3.74	0.47	GE
9. discuss what is relevant to keep the interaction focused.	3.71	0.47	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.71	0.34	GE

Table 2
English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Restriction and Turn taking

	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
1. use minimal responses.	3.10	0.59	ME
2. exclude other topics not included in the nomination.	3.23	0.68	ME
3. explain some rules to follow in the conduct of the class.	3.60	0.55	GE
4. employ visual signals to give clues.	3.53	0.55	GE
5. tell students to answer reasonably.	3.55	0.55	GE
6. wait for someone to stop speaking.	3.52	0.59	GE
7. ask a follow up questions.	3.64	0.51	GE
8. give everyone a chance to speak.	3.70	0.47	GE
9. allow students to express their reactions.	3.78	0.42	GE
10. ask students' opinion.	3.74	0.47	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.54	0.35	GE

Table 3

English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of topic control and shifting

	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
focus on the topic.	3.82	0.42	GE
entertain relevant questions.	3.74	0.47	GE
avoid unnecessary interruptions.	3.57	0.55	GE
ask a question to clarify the message.	3.74	0.45	GE
give some transitional signals.	3.59	0.56	GE
end a conversation and beginning a new one.	3.57	0.55	GE
move to one topic smoothly.	3.62	0.51	GE
make sure that the previous topic was nurtured.	3.70	0.47	GE
emphasize the important parts of the topics.	3.77	0.44	GE
create a mutual agreement.	3.60	0.57	GE
limit the topics that will be discussed.	3.52	0.59	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.66	0.37	GE

Table 4

English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Repair

	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
take initiative to set the conversation back to its topic.	3.62	0.52	GE
show appreciation to all.	3.82	0.38	GE
give others the opportunity to speak.	3.76	0.45	GE
correct students' wrong answers appropriately.	3.73	0.48	GE
ask for replacement on apparently glaring errors or mistakes.	3.53	0.56	GE
initiate things for improvement.	3.67	0.50	GE
repeat what was discussed.	3.37	0.66	ME
use hesitation pauses.	3.20	0.77	ME
make sure that everyone is being enlightened.	3.68	0.53	GE
search for a word.	3.51	0.59	GE
start their utterance wrongly.	3.00	0.96	ME
employ instantaneous repetitions.	3.15	0.79	ME
give students time to think.	3.71	0.49	GE
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.52	0.40	GE

Table 5

English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of termination

	W.M.	S.D.	V.I.
give a signal to end the session.	3.54	0.55	GE
use concluding cues.	3.60	0.49	GE
share insights.	3.72	0.51	GE
solicit agreement.	3.55	0.53	GE
leave a question to reflect on.	3.56	0.58	GE
assert clear closure.	3.61	0.50	GE
confirm that students are enlightened.	3.72	0.48	GE
say a catchy line.	3.45	0.59	ME
leave a quotation.	3.35	0.66	ME
summarize the lesson.	3.66	0.52	GE
prolong by giving clarifications.	3.34	0.67	ME
discuss the continuation of the topic.	3.49	0.62	ME
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.55	0.41	GE

Table 6.1
Students' Communication Strategies as Assessed by English Language Teachers

INTRAPERSONAL	W.M	S.D.	V.I.
Using different communicative strategies. Students are able to...			
1.build self-confidence in expressing thoughts, feelings , and emotions.	3.65	0.53	A
2.raise emotional awareness towards someone.	3.48	0.53	I
3.conduct self-assessment to improve oneself.	3.61	0.50	A
4.manage self-awareness to monitor one's world.	3.57	0.50	A
5. possess persistence to make firm decisions.	3.57	0.51	A
6. have self-control to avoid temptations.	3.62	0.50	A
7. open to new ideas for more knowledge.	3.57	0.51	A
8. make wise time management decisions to do things on time	3.50	0.52	A
9. overcome distractions to maximize time.	3.50	0.52	A
10. create resilience to promote positivity at all time.	3.37	0.63	I
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.54	0.52	GE

Table 6.2
Students' Communication Strategies as Assessed by English Language Teachers

INTERPERSONAL different communicative strategies. Students are able to...	Using	W.M.	S.D.	I
1.give and collect information that will further help other people.		3.59	0.49	A
2.influence the attitudes and behaviors of others.		3.57	0.51	A
3.form contacts and maintain relationships.		3.58	0.52	A
4.make sense of the world and our experiences in it.		3.66	0.48	A
5.express personal needs and understand the needs of others.		3.56	0.53	A
6.give and receive emotional support to maintain a harmonious relationship.		3.55	0.51	A
7.make decisions and solve problems to build connections with other people.		3.31	0.67	I
8.anticipate and predict behavior that helps in decision-making.		3.55	0.54	A
9.regulate power towards other people		3.31	0.67	i
10.provide leadership and reassurance to those around you.		3.31	0.67	I
COMPOSITE MEAN		3.50	0.55	GE

Table 7.1

Relationship between the extent of the respondents' utilization of communicative strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal.

	R-value	R^2 - value	p -value	Decision on H0	Interpretation
Nomination	0.4764	0.2269	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Restriction and Turn taking	0.5672	0.3217	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Topic control and shifting	0.4940	0.2440	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Repair	0.4286	0.1837	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Termination	0.5179	0.2682	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant

Table 7.2
Relationship between the extent of the respondents' utilization of communicative strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to interpersonal.

	R-value	R^2 - value	p -value	Decision on H0	Interpretation
Nomination	0.5136	0.2638	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Restriction and Turn taking	0.5991	0.3589	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Topic control and shifting	0.5607	0.3144	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Repair	0.4928	0.2429	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant
Termination	0.5718	0.3270	0.0000	Failed to Reject	Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1- English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Nomination

It can be seen in the table that the respondents assessed that nomination with a Great Extent has a composite mean of 3.71. Meanwhile, among the indicators in terms of nomination, the respondents assessed as the highest weighted mean 3.75 is the composite mean of saying what is relevant to the topic. In other words, the related topics would only be given room in the class discussion. Irrelevant questions were not entertained by the teacher.

In connection, learning methods are important in facilitating the successful learning of a second or foreign language (L2) and have received a lot of attention in the literature (Griffiths, 2013; Oxford, 2003, 2017).

Moreover, according to Thompson (2020) students develop complex thinking skills with the aid of rigor and relevance. Students will need to collaborate with people from different backgrounds in teams both inside and outside of the classroom in order to make decisions and finish challenging tasks. Relevance makes learning meaningful for kids, while rigor makes sure they are pushed to master more difficult concepts. Since they guarantee that all students have access to and entrance points to high-level information and skills, rigor and relevance are equally crucial for equity.

Second to the highest got a weighted mean of 3.74 in establishing the topic clearly. It means that it is evident that this strategy has been widely used by the respondents. In other words, this will be helpful to avoid confusions in teaching. With that, students can easily understand the lessons that has been delivered by the teacher.

Stating the objectives clearly at the start of the class is third to the highest who has a weighted mean of 3.73. It means that most of the respondents give importance to the objectives in class. In fact, when displayed to students, learning objectives set student expectations, guide their learning processes, and help them focus their study time for the upcoming examination.

The development of appropriate and unambiguous learning outcomes can benefit both teachers and students. Learning outcomes provide teachers with the ability to clearly understand the learning materials, strategies to be employed, types of learning activities/tasks that will be assigned, the right form of assessment, and make it easier to evaluate learning, Mahajan & Singh (2017).

Moreover, as stated in the study of Zhou (2017) learning objectives provide a guide for students when reviewing materials and preparing for assessments. Learning objectives are the most powerful if they are actionable and measurable. Likewise, it helps instructors select and organize course content, and determine the types of assessments and learning activities to build for a course.

Table 2-English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Restriction and Turn Taking

Table 2 shows the extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Restriction and Turn taking which has a composite mean of 3.54. The highest indicator got a weighted mean of 3.78 which explains that respondents allow students to express their reactions. It simply means that teachers are open in any kind of reaction coming from the students. As a result, it build a harmonious relationship between the students and the teacher.

In connection with this, in the study of Chitra (2013) he mentioned that team projects, group presentations, in-class and online debates, and collective problem solving are examples of collaborative academic activities that necessitate active knowledge sharing. When these activities are properly integrated into the instructional design, learning can become more dynamic and engaging. Many studies show that collaborative learning, which involves active knowledge sharing, provides many benefits to students, including improved academic achievement, improved communication and interpersonal skills, appreciation for diverse ideas and viewpoints, positive interdependence, and a sense of fulfillment for contributing to others' learning.

Asking students' opinion got a weighted mean of 3.74. It is the highest indicator among the ten indicators. It is because the more the teacher value student's creativity and help them see their value, the more they will recognize themselves and the more they will be motivated in class.

Furthermore, motivation drives learners to complete their learning tasks. Griffiths (2013) argued that external and internal motivation influence learners to become successful. Therefore, learners with positive experiences may become motivated, but this can be challenging in an environment where mixed-ability learners are present. That is, the learners' confidence level in language learning can scaffold or hinder their language learning.

Third to the highest indicator is giving everyone a chance to speak. It has a weighted mean of 3.74. In fact, listening to others is a necessary leadership ability for all. The listener learns more than the speaker because he or she has a chance to think about what they have heard, compare the information they have gotten and their understanding. It is similar to a learning process since a person get to hear what others are thinking about, not just self-thoughts. Moreover, enabling

everyone to speak gives the listener several ideas and exposes him or her to different points of view.

This is related to the study of (Caruso, Colombi, & Tebbit, 2017) which explains that 'listening' component of communication should not be overlooked – over 60% of all misunderstandings result from poor listening. Teachers as well as students can gain from practicing attentive listening in the classroom in two different ways. First of all, by setting an example to students, they will become better listeners and learn information more effectively. Additionally, the teacher may clarify misconceptions and expand learning using active listening, giving your kids a better education.

Table 3- English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of topic control and shifting

The explanation of teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of topic control and shifting can be seen in Table 3. It has a composite mean of 3.66 and the highest indicator got 3.82 which means focusing in class plays a vital role in class. The respondents believed that one must concentrate and give more attention on the topic in class.

There are several stimulants that are required and not required which is vital for classroom learning, and these distracting cues can easily induce pupils to shift their attention. Despite this, pupils are expected to maintain exceptional attention in the classroom. Thus, utilization of teachers' strategies are very important. (Szpunar, Moulton & Schacter, 2013).

Second to the highest got a composite mean of 3.77 which indicates that emphasizing the important parts of the topics is highly regarded. It means that the English language teacher is highlighting the important parts of the topic. It is also a strategy to draw attention to important information in a lesson. Effective highlighting is good because it first asks the students to pick out the important parts, and then gives an effective way to review that information later.

In addition, Manju (2015) concentrated on the efficiency of communication accommodations in English teaching and discovered that teachers utilized convergence tactics such as modifying discourse to achieve. Obtain approval from students or build effective engagement. Teachers also employed divergence methods, according to the findings.

Entertaining relevant questions and asking a question to clarify the message got the third highest composite mean which is 3.74. Specifically, questions which are only related in class will be answered by the teacher. If there will be cases that students will raise unrelated questions. The teacher will disregard him or her.

Also, asking a question to clarify the message means that the students are very much welcome to ask questions. It is believed that this aids in eliminating or preventing any misunderstanding, confusion or ambiguity in any class discussion. By asking this type of question after receiving the message, the teacher and the student makes sure they properly understood the message to obtain the important additional information.

Table 4- English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of Repair

The fourth table shows English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of repair, and it has a composite mean of 3.52. Showing

appreciate to all has the highest weighted mean which has 3.82. Moreover, the most important thing in class is to positively affirm students' learning behavior. In addition, keeping students in a pleasant condition during the learning process in order to maximize education and teaching impacts was taken into consideration.

Teachers who foster positive relationships with their students create classroom environments more conducive to learning and meet students' developmental, emotional, and academic needs. Thus, giving others the opportunity to speak got the weighted mean of 3.76. In connection with this, giving students the opportunity to speak in a classroom setting can keep them motivated and interested in learning. In the classroom, some students easily answer questions because they are not afraid of speaking publicly, while others do not try because they lack similar confidence.

Therefore, according to Trust 2021, to foster healthy relationships between students and those in charge of their education, adults must address the long-standing harms brought on by racism in schools. Implicit and explicit bias and prejudice can easily result in damaging school policies that erase kids' cultural identities. However, it is crucial to purposefully create relationships with students of color while keeping in mind their needs and using a strengths-based perspective that acknowledges and honors the valuable cultural and linguistic contributions they provide to the classroom.

Moreover, correcting students' wrong answers appropriately has a weighted mean of 3.73. As a matter of fact, making mistakes is an important learning opportunity. Learning is enhanced by error, whether it involves doing homework, making friends, or participating in sports. Students learn persistence when developing new skills, along with how to build resiliency to failure when they make mistake.

Khansir and Pakdel (201a) added that "most of errors among the students can be replaced by remedial measures through the instructional materials and teachings-learning strategies"(p.536). On the other hand, in their study, it has been mentioned that some of the student's errors may be due to mistakes and carelessness and they preferred that all the student's errors are not necessary for requiring the same remedial treatment.

Table 5-English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of termination

It can be reflected in Table 5 the English language teachers' extent of utilization of different communicative strategies in terms of termination and it has a composite mean of 3.55. The highest weighted mean is 3.72 which indicates that sharing insights and confirming that students are enlightened are regarded as highly important.

More so, sharing insights gauge inspiring and fueling the flame of passion in humans. Positive words of gratitude and important knowledge offered aid in the development of every student. Sharing information has an induction effect on others, allowing them to expand their knowledge as well as with oneself.

As added by Davis 2014, students will get to know one another better and form kind, family-like ties in the classroom when they are sharing in class. Additionally, students will discover effective ways to interact with their peers. The advantages of partner, dialogue, and around-the-circle sharing for student learning are endless.

Additionally, summarizing the lesson has a weighted mean of 3.66. This is how the teacher distill lengthy passages of text down to their most important components: the core elements that are important to note and retain. Summarizing is one of the most challenging tactics to teach and one of the most challenging strategies for pupils to fully understand. Summarizing is essential because students gain the ability to identify key concepts and gather evidence to support those concepts. It enables pupils to concentrate on the important words and phrases in each book that they should remember.

As a matter of fact, using learning strategies to enhance students' literacy has been recognized as an important approach of teaching Sung et al., 2015, among the proposed strategies, summarizing is one of the most recommended strategies for developing reading and writing skills, Lenhard et al., 2013.

The third to the highest weighted mean has 3.35 which falls under leaving a question to reflect on. Similarly, students gain the ability to identify key concepts and gather evidence to support those concepts. It enables pupils to concentrate on the important words and phrases in a given book that they should remember.

Furthermore, Shea 2021 mentioned that reflection questions offer us a sense of success and aid in recalling lessons learned. When we carefully reflect on our struggles and successes, we can find rewarding moments and things we can strive to do differently in the future. Students can take ownership of their learning and see that they can overcome difficult tasks if they put their minds to it when you assist them in setting attainable goals. Reflection serves as a basis for lifelong learning and encourages pride in newly acquired skills, particularly metacognition abilities that assist students in recognizing their own development.

Table 6.1- Students' Communication Strategies as Assessed by English Language Teachers

As shown in the findings, intrapersonal has a composite mean of 3.54. Build self-confidence in expressing thoughts, feelings, and emotions got the highest weighted mean. In connection with this, intrapersonal abilities allow you to manage emotions and deal with obstacles throughout your life. Intrapersonal talents, like emotional intelligence, include self-confidence, persistence, being open to change and new ideas, ability to overcome distractions, time management, resilience and self-discipline, (Stephens 2022).

As matter of fact, intrapersonal skills enable us to accomplish as much as possible in life. Knowing our strengths and weaknesses can help us perform better at work and in our personal life. Because we can regulate our emotions, deal with problems, and learn from our experiences, good intrapersonal abilities help us create and maintain both personal and professional connections with others.

Recent research indicates that the extent to which people engage in self-control metacognition is related to how successfully they deal with diverse self-control problems in everyday life (Bürgler & Hennecke, 2022; Bürgler et al., 2021). Such self-control conflicts arise when people are required to initiate or continue in aversive activities, as well as when they are required to repress powerful responses to temptations (Hennecke et al., 2019; Hoyle & Davisson, 2016). Moreover, these studies are related to self-control to avoid temptations which has a weighted mean of 3.62.

In addition, conducting self-assessment to improve oneself was considered as the third highest among all. It has a weighted mean of 3.61. In fact, self-assessment provides students with an

opportunity to self-evaluate, or make judgments about their learning process and products of learning, based on criteria that they have agreed on with their instructor.

Self-evaluation and self-reflection are effective ways to improve a student's learning experience. It is critical in educating students not only what to study, but also how to learn and how to enhance their learning results. By including exercises that require students to critically reflect on their work, methods, and learning style, they are able to detect holes in their knowledge or skill set, resulting in increased autonomy, deeper learning, and metacognition.

New conceptions of self-assessment are grounded in theories of the self- and co-regulation of learning (Andrade and Brookhart, 2016), which includes self-monitoring of learning processes with and without explicit standards.

Butler (2018) points out that her research adds to our empirical knowledge of the ways in which children respond to self-evaluation. This is a very positive development for the industry. Our understanding of how and why self-assessment affects learning and performance would likely significantly advance if similar studies of processing during formative self-assessment of a range of task types in a classroom situation were conducted.

Table 6.2

It was evident that the composite mean is 3.50 and the highest weighted mean is 3.66 which corresponds to making sense of the world and our experiences in it. In connection with this, each of our five senses—sight, hearing, touch, taste, and smell—seems to function separately as a different way to see the world. But in fact, they work together closely to help the mind comprehend its environment. We can learn about this partnership in specific situations.

In some cases, a sense may covertly influence the one we think is dominant. When visual information clashes with that from sound, sensory crosstalk can cause what we see to alter what we hear. When one sense drops out, another can pick up the slack. For instance, people who are blind can train their hearing to play double duty. Those who are both blind and deaf can make touch step in—to say, help them interpret speech. For a few individuals with a condition called synesthesia, the senses collide dramatically to form a kaleidoscope world in which chicken tastes like triangles, a symphony smells of baked bread or words bask in a halo of red, green or purple, Groeger (2012).

Give and collect information that will further help other people has a weighted mean of 3.59. By assisting you in accurately expressing your ideas and intentions, interpersonal communication skills can aid your personal and professional relationships. Your listening abilities will also help you better comprehend and empathize with people.

Being a good listener is one of the most crucial elements of creating strong relationships. Healthy partnerships depend on active listening. It demonstrates your respect for the other person's ideas and emotions as well as your curiosity in what they have to say. Having effective communication is crucial for establishing trust. You can make better decisions and resolve conflicts by carefully listening in order to better comprehend the other person's viewpoint. This strengthens the tie between people in a relationship and promotes respect for one another. A connection can also be strengthened and kept strong by consistently expressing gratitude and admiration to the other person.

In connection, as stated by Haven, 2023, a meaningful life depends on developing and preserving strong relationships. It enables people to establish meaningful connections with others and feel a sense of belonging. Relationships are important to our general well-being

because they can offer companionship, support, and affection. Healthy relationships involve time, effort, and communication, whether they are with a love partner, a family member, a friend, or a coworker.

Third to the highest got the weighted mean of 3.58 which has an indicator of forming contacts and maintaining relationships. Total physical and emotional well-being depends on one's interpersonal relationships. Relationships give you a sense of purpose in life and combat loneliness. For instance, a key component of your social support system is the closeness you feel to your family and friends.

More employee recognition is a result of effective interpersonal communication. Employees are more inclined to compliment one another's work and offer helpful criticism when they get along well with one another and their superiors.

Table 7.1 and 7.2- Relationship between the extent of the respondents' utilization of communicative strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal.

Table 11 presents the relationship between the respondents' utilization of communicative strategies and the intrapersonal and interpersonal as assessed by the teachers. It can be gleaned from the above table that there is moderate correlation between the teachers' utilization of communicative strategies in terms of nomination and the intrapersonal and interpersonal skills. This is confirmed by the computed R – value of 0.4764 with p – value less than 0.05 level of significance. Result of the study also shows that 22.69% of the total variability of the respondents' level of competence in terms of modelling is explained by their utilization of communicative strategies.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. English teachers find it significant to use different communicative strategies such as nomination, restriction and turn taking, topic control and shifting, repair; and termination.
2. English language teachers perceived communication strategies as great extent in all aspects of the instruction of the teacher during class.
3. English language teachers believe that there is significant relationship between the extent of utilization of comm strategies and students' communication strategies as assessed by the teacher as to intrapersonal and interpersonal.
4. Workshop Matrix is needed to further improve teaching strategies in class.

Recommendations

As extracted from the conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. The school administrators may review the strategies being utilized by the teachers to ensure that all of them are teaching effectively.
2. English teachers may always consider integration of communicative strategies.
3. The school administrators may allot the budget for the conduct of seminars, trainings, and workshops of the teachers to equip them with knowledge on how to teach effectively.

4. Teachers may adapt and use the proposed Workshop Guidelines, a set of strategies for English Language Teachers.
5. Future researchers may further conduct a similar study to further validate the results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares her commitment to upholding established ethical norms and principles within the context of her research. These principles include gaining informed permission from participants, safeguarding their privacy and confidentiality, and mitigating potential harm or risks. In addition, the open management of data, the acknowledgment of conflicts of interest, and the precise documentation of results are fundamental elements of ethical research. By adhering to these principles, not only are the rights and well-being of individuals participating upheld, but the overall ethical standing of the scientific community is also preserved. This, in turn, fosters public trust in research and its outcomes.

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REFERENCES

- Andrade, H., and Brookhart, S. M. (2016). "The role of classroom assessment in supporting self-regulated learning," in *Assessment for Learning: Meeting the Challenge of Implementation*, eds D. Laveault and L. Allal (Heidelberg: Springer), 293–309. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-39211-0_17
- Anya S. (2022). What Are Intrapersonal Skills and Why Are They Important. Retrieved from <https://www.peoplesense.com.au/news/article/13052022-239/what-are-intrapersonal-skills-and-why-are-they-important>
- Baruah, S. & Goswami, U. (2012). Factors influencing school dropouts at the primary level. *International Journal of Farm Sciences* 2(1) :141-144
https://www.academia.edu/31782945/Factors_influencing_school_dropouts_at_the_primary_level
- Bürgler, M. Hennecke et al. (2022) Smart Strategy-Use: Metacognition, Strategy Repertoire, and Polyregulation in Daily Self-Control Conflicts retrieved from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/sjop.12964>
- Butler, Y. G. (2018). "Young learners' processes and rationales for responding to self-assessment items: cases for generic can-do and five-point Likert-type formats," in

- Useful Assessment and Evaluation in Language Education, eds J. Davis et al. (Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press), 21–39. doi: 10.2307/j.ctvvngrq.5
- Caruso, Marinella & Colombi, Anna & Tebbit, Simon. (2017). Teaching how to Listen. Blended Learning for the Development and Assessment of Listening Skills in a Second Language. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*. 14. 10.53761/1.14.1.7.
- Chitra, K. (2013) .Role of Knowledge Sharing in the Learning Process. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262912309_Role_of_Knowledge_Sharing_in_the_Learning_Process
- Flores, R. (2016). Oral Communication in Context. Rex Book Store, Inc retrieved from: <http://mololibrary.jblfmu.edu.ph/Oral.communication.in.context.by.Ramona.Flores.pdf>
- Griffiths, C. (2013). The strategy factor in successful language learning. *Multilingual Matters*. [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(lz5mqp453edsnp55rrgjt55\)\)/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2946736](https://www.scirp.org/(S(lz5mqp453edsnp55rrgjt55))/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2946736)
- Groeger L. (2012). Making Sense of the World, Several Senses at a Time retrieved from: <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/making-sense-world-sveral-senses-at-time/>
- Goodwin, B. & Miller, K. (2012). Research says good feedback is targeted, specific, timely. *Educational Leadership*, 70(1), 82–83. Retrieved from <http://www.ascd.org/publications/educational-leadership/sept12/vol70/num01/Good-Feedback-Is-Targeted,-Specific,-Timely.aspx> Link
- Khansir, A. A., & Pakdel, F. (2018). Study of Errors and English Language Teaching: A Systematic Review. *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 4(12), 531-538.
- W. Lenhard, H. Baier, D. Endlich, W. Schneider, J. (2013) Hoffmann Rethinking strategy instruction: direct reading strategy instruction versus computer-based guided practice *Journal of Research in Reading*, 36 (2) (2013), pp. 223-240.
- Laal, M. & Ghodsi, S. M. (2012). Benefits of collaborative learning. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 31 (2012) 486 – 490.
- Mahajan M. & Singh M. (2017).Importance and Benefits of Learning Outcomes. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* Volume 22, Issue 3, Ver. V (March. 2017) PP 65-67 .
- Manju, G. (2015). Effectiveness of Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT) in Teaching of English as a Second Language in India. *GNOSIS*, 1(3), 224-234.
- Mayer J. D., Stevens A. A. (1994). An emerging understanding of the reflective (meta-) experience of mood. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 28, 371–373; *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 31 (2012) 486 – 490.
- Nagy, W.E. and Townsend, D. 2012, Words as tools: Learning academic vocabulary as language acquisition, *Reading Research Quarterly*, 47 (1): 91-108.
- Shea, A. (2021). Teaching Young Students How to Reflect on Their Learning retrieved from: <https://www.edutopia.org/article/teaching-young-students-how-reflect-their-learning/>
- Sung, Y. T (2013. , Chang, T. H., Lin, W. C., Hsieh, K. S., & Chang, K. E. CRIE: An automated analyzer for Chinese texts. *Behavior Research Method*. (in press). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3758/s13428-015-0649-1>
- Szpunar, K. K., Moulton, S. T., & Schacter, D. L. (2013). Mind wandering and education: From the classroom to online learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 495. retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00495>
- Thompson, J. (2020). The importance of adding rigor and relevance to instruction. retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276025849_Rigor_and_Responsiveness_in_Classroom_Activity

- Trust, E. (2021). The Importance of Strong Relationships: A Strategy to Solve Unfinished Learning. retrieved from: <https://edtrust.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/The-Importance-of-Strong-Relationships-as-a-Strategy-to-Solve-Unfinished-Learning-March-2021.pdf>
- Oxford, R. (2017). Teaching and Researching Language Learning Strategies: Self-Regulation in Context (2nd edition). Routledge
- Varbanov, R. (2015). The Potential of Social Media for the Business of Companies. Business Management, 1(3), 5–28.
- Washbourne, A., 2013, Word Power Pilot: Improving reading for meaning through expanding vocabulary, Croydon retrieved from: <https://www.bell-foundation.org.uk/eal-programme/guidance/effective-teaching-of-eal-learners/great-ideas/modelling/>
- Wiggins, G. (2012). Seven keys to effective feedback. Educational Leadership, 70(1), 10–16. Retrieved from <https://www.ascd.org/publications/educational%20leadership/sept12/vol70/num01/seven-keys-to-effective-feedback.asp>
- Zhou, H. (2017). Why Does Writing Good Learning Objectives Matter?. retrieved from: <https://learninginnovation.duke.edu/blog/2017/03/learning-objectives/>